

CERTAINTY NOA's DMP

Version 0

Description

The Data Management Plan (DMP) for ground based remote sensing observational data, radiative transfer calculations, as well as scattering datasets created at the National Observatory of Athens (NOA) is developed in the context of effectively managing and preserving valuable data generated for CERTAINTY project.

The DMP for ground based remote sensing observational data, radiative transfer calculations, as well as scattering datasets at NOA is designed to maximize the value, accessibility, and impact of the data produced, supporting the Institute's mission in advancing meteorological research and services.

Funder

European Commission||EC

Grant

CERTAINTY

Researchers

Dimitra Kouklaki (orcid:0000-0001-8652-0442), Kyriakoula Papachristopoulou (orcid:0000-0001-8000-5714), Konstantinos Rizos (orcid:0009-0000-1038-4376), Alexandra Tsekeri (orcid:0000-0002-3745-225X), Kalliopi Artemis Voudouri (orcid:0000-0002-9190-4608), Vassilis Amiridis

(orcid:0000-0002-1544-7812), ELENI DRAKAKI (orcid:0000-0001-8568-5114), Anna Gialitaki (orcid:0000-0001-9270-8361), Ioanna Tsikoudi (orcid:0000-0001-7858-1667), Maria Tsihla (orcid:0009-0005-9089-2843), Eleni Marinou (orcid:0000-0003-2631-6057), Peristera Paschou (orcid:0000-0002-9783-1024), Athanasios Georgiou (orcid:0000-0002-2940-5672)

Organizations

Finnish Meteorological Institute, National Observatory of Athens

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: CERTAINTY NOA's DMP

Description:

The Data Management Plan (DMP) for ground based remote sensing observational data, radiative transfer calculations, as well as scattering datasets created at the National Observatory of Athens (NOA) is developed in the context of effectively managing and preserving valuable data generated for CERTAINTY project.

The DMP for ground based remote sensing observational data, radiative transfer calculations, as well as scattering datasets at NOA is designed to maximize the value, accessibility, and impact of the data produced, supporting the Institute's mission in advancing meteorological research and services.

Researchers:

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Vassilis Amiridis (orcid:0000-0002-1544-7812)
ELENI DRAKAKI (orcid:0000-0001-8568-5114)
Anna Gialitaki (orcid:0000-0001-9270-8361)
Ioanna Tsikoudi (orcid:0000-0001-7858-1667)
Maria Tsichla (orcid:0009-0005-9089-2843)
Eleni Marinou (orcid:0000-0003-2631-6057)
Peristera Paschou (orcid:0000-0002-9783-1024)
Athanasios Georgiou (orcid:0000-0002-2940-5672)

Organizations:

Finnish Meteorological Institute
National Observatory of Athens

Contact: Anca Hienola

2. Funding

Funding organizations: [European Commission](#)||[EC](#)

Grants: [CERTAINTY](#)

Project: [CERTAINTY](#)

3. License

License: [CC-BY-4.0](#)

Access Rights: [Public](#)

4. Templates

Descriptions

Radiative transfer simulations

Radiative transfer calculations to estimate aerosol and clouds radiative effect using newly developed scattering datasets

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

New

The calculations will be performed during the project as part of WP1.

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Simulation

Spectral short wave and long wave irradiances at bottom of the atmosphere (BOA) and top of the atmosphere (TOA), and radiometric quantities profiles

1.1.5 What is its format?

ascii

netcdf

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

3000000000000

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To obtain information
- To share information
- To make informed decisions
- To combine with other data

Data will be used to study processes, interpret observations, and derive aerosol-cloud interactions.

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

The following radiative transfer programs will be utilized to perform the needed calculations:

1) The libRadtran model, publicly available under GNU licence in:
<https://www.libradtran.org/doku.php>

2) The MCstar (Monte Carlo solver for 3D radiative transfer simulations), available at: <http://157.82.240.167/~clastr/>, upon request from the developers

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities

- Decision makers

Project partners

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

No

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

No

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

No

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

Data identifiers

DOI

Simulations output will be provided through Zenodo linked to DOI

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

DataCite Metadata Schema

Metadata will be provided through Zenodo

3.1.1.3 What type(s) of metadata?

Descriptive

We offer descriptive metadata that enriches data or information resources with detailed information about their content, context, and structure, thereby improving their findability and practical use.

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

No

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

Yes

3.1.1.7 How are searchable metadata provided?

- Registry/Catalogue
- Metadata repository

The NOA's metadata can be found in OPENAIRE (<https://explore.openaire.eu>) and EOSC-portal ([EOSC-portal.eu](https://eosc-portal.eu))

3.1.1.8 Are keywords provided in the metadata?

Yes

3.1.1.9 Are metadata harvestable?

Yes

Metadata can be harvested for data sharing through the Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting (OAI-PMH).

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

Zenodo

3.2.1.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?

Yes

- Follows repository standards
- Details terms of use
- Has an open access content policy
- Supports retention
- Follows metadata standards
- Supports mid- and long-term preservation
- Has data security mechanisms in place

3.2.1.5 Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?

Yes

3.2.1.6 Does the repository(ies) resolve the identifiers to a digital object?

Zenodo automatically register a DOI for a record once it is published

3.2.1.7 Does the repository support versioning?

Yes

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

Radiative transfer calculations for aerosol and clouds radiative effect

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open

Open, although a certain embargo period might be applied

3.2.2.5 Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset / output?

No

3.2.2.8 Is the described dataset / output supported by a data access committee?

No

3.2.2.9 Please specify how the dataset / output will be accessed during and after the project ends

Throughout the project's duration, the dataset might be subject to an embargo of up to two years. During this period, access to the data will be restricted, but project partners can obtain access using specific tokens. Once the embargo period concludes and the project is completed, the dataset will become publicly available, and accessible to all under the CC BY 4.0 license.

After the data become publicly accessible, it will not be possible to identify individuals who access the data. However, during the embargo period, access is controlled through tokens that are nominally issued to specific, selected partners.

3.2.2.10 Please specify how long after the project has ended the dataset / output will be made accessible for

Items will be retained for the lifetime of the repository in Zenodo. This is currently the lifetime of the host laboratory CERN, which currently has an experimental programme defined for the next 20 years at least.

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

Yes

Yes. However, we will not have closed datasets

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.3 Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?

Yes

Direct links are provided

3.2.3.4 Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?

Yes

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

3.3.3 Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?

Yes

DataCite Metadata Schema

3.3.7 Does the described dataset / output provide qualified references with other outputs?

Yes

The dataset will be linked with the related scientific articles.

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

The embargo period is 2 years from the moment of publication of the dataset.

3.4.2 What reusability and / or reproducibility methods are followed?

- Readme files
- Data cleaning
- Analyses
- Variable definitions
- Units of measurement
- Negative results sharing

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

Yes

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

Yes

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

Yes

Input data provenance will be linked in the metadata.

3.4.6 What documented procedures for quality assurance do you have in place?

- Data conform to format specification
- Consistency verified with data models and standards

We will compare the simulated data with available measurements.

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

0

Euro

- Storage
- Archiving
- Re-use
- Security

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Other

Data will be provided through Zenodo

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

Anna Gialitaki (orcid:0000-0001-9270-8361)

5.1 Data Security

5.1.1 What security measures are followed?

Passwords

5.1.2 What conditions do the security measures meet?

- Data access
- Data storage
- Data transmission
- Data recovery
- Data sharing

5.1.3 How will you preserve the described dataset / output in the long term?

Items will be retained for the lifetime of the repository in Zenodo. This is currently the lifetime of the host laboratory CERN, which currently has an experimental programme defined for the next 20 years at least.

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

no

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

No

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

Yes

7.1.2 Documentation of other procedures

All the minimum conditions listed in Science Europe Guidance Document are covered by the WP6 Open Science and Data management

Assimilation Operators software

This dataset refers to software, specifically the set of "observation operators" that are developed during the project. Often, observations are for physical quantities that are not part of a numerical weather prediction model's state. Thus, these functions calculate the expected observation from the model state and enable assimilation of such observations.

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Software

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

New

The code will be developed during the project as part of WP2.

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Other

1.1.5 What is its format?

Source code files.

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

Negligible

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To obtain information
- To share information
- To make informed decisions
- To develop a product
- To improve a product
- To combine with other data

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

The software will be developed during the project as part of WP2.

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- Decision makers

Project partners

Additionally, the software might prove useful to researchers investigating assimilation applications of novel observations.

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

No

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

No

2.2 Datasets

2.2.1 Does the described output use or support any published dataset?

No

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

Data identifiers

DOI

Source codes will be provided through Github and a Zenodo mirror, linked to a DOI.

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

DataCite Metadata Schema

Metadata will be provided through Zenodo

3.1.1.3 What type(s) of metadata?

Descriptive

In addition, ReadMe files will be added.

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

No

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

Yes

3.1.1.7 How are searchable metadata provided?

- Registry/Catalogue
- Metadata repository

3.1.1.8 Are keywords provided in the metadata?

Yes

software, numerical model operators

3.1.1.9 Are metadata harvestable?

Yes

Metadata can be harvested for data sharing through the Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting (OAI-PMH).

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?

Yes

- Follows repository standards
- Details terms of use
- Has an open access content policy
- Supports retention
- Follows metadata standards
- Supports mid- and long-term preservation
- Has data security mechanisms in place

3.2.1.5 Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?

Yes

3.2.1.6 Does the repository(ies) resolve the identifiers to a digital object?

Zenodo automatically register a DOI for a record once it is published

3.2.1.7 Does the repository support versioning?

Yes

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

This dataset refers to software, specifically the set of "observation operators" that are developed during the project. Often, observations are for physical quantities that are not part of a numerical weather prediction model's state. Thus, these functions calculate the expected observation from the model state and enable assimilation of such observations.

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open

Open, although a certain embargo period might be applied

3.2.2.5 Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset / output?

No

3.2.2.8 Is the described dataset / output supported by a data access committee?

No

3.2.2.9 Please specify how the dataset / output will be accessed during and after the project ends

Throughout the project's duration, the software might be subject to an embargo of up to two years. During this period, access to the data will be restricted, but project partners can obtain access using specific tokens. Once the embargo period concludes and the project is completed, the software will become publicly available, and accessible to all under the GNU Public License v2.

After the software become publicly accessible, it will not be possible to identify individuals who access the software. However, during the embargo period, access is controlled through tokens that are nominally issued to specific, selected partners.

3.2.2.10 Please specify how long after the project has ended the dataset / output will be made accessible for

Items will be retained for the lifetime of the repository in Zenodo. This is currently the lifetime of the host laboratory CERN, which currently has an experimental programme defined for the next 20 years at least.

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

Yes

Yes. However, we will not have closed datasets

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.3 Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?

Yes

Direct links are provided

3.2.3.4 Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?

Yes

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

3.3.3 Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?

Yes

DataCite Metadata Schema

3.3.7 Does the described dataset / output provide qualified references with other outputs?

Yes

The dataset will be linked with the related scientific articles and also with the input data.

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?

GNU General Public License 2.0

The embargo period is 2 years from the moment of publication.

3.4.2 What reusability and / or reproducibility methods are followed?

- Readme files
- Other

Sample scripts and/or notebooks

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

Yes

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

Yes

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

Yes

Input data provenance will be linked in the metadata.

3.4.6 What documented procedures for quality assurance do you have in place?

- Data conform to format specification
- Consistency verified with data models and standards

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

0

Euro

- Storage
- Archiving
- Re-use
- Security

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Other

Code will be provided through Zenodo

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

Anna Gialitaki (orcid:0000-0001-9270-8361)

5.1 Data Security

5.1.2 What conditions do the security measures meet?

- Data access
- Data storage
- Data transmission
- Data recovery
- Data sharing

5.1.3 How will you preserve the described dataset / output in the long term?

Items will be retained for the lifetime of the repository in Zenodo. This is currently the lifetime of the host laboratory CERN, which currently has an experimental programme defined for the next 20 years at least.

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

no

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

No

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

Yes

7.1.2 Documentation of other procedures

All the minimum conditions listed in Science Europe Guidance Document are covered by the WP6 Open Science and Data management

Scattering datasets

Newly developed aerosol scattering datasets assuming different aerosol types (i.e. dust, smoke, marine aerosols), realistic size (i.e. super-coarse dust) and shape distributions.

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

New

The calculations will be performed during the project as part of WP1.

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Simulation

Single scattering properties of polydisperse randomly oriented aerosol particles of different types (i.e., dust, marine, smoke, urban aerosols)

1.1.5 What is its format?

netcdf

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

3000000

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To obtain information

- To share information
- To develop a product
- To improve a product
- To combine with other data

Data will be used to study processes, interpret observations, and derive aerosol-cloud interactions.

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

Various scattering codes and databases will be utilized to produce the new scattering datasets including:

1) The ADDA software for arbitrary shaped particles, publicly available in github: <https://github.com/adda-team/adda>

2) The Tmatrix software for rotationally symmetric particles, publicly available: <https://www.giss.nasa.gov/staff/mmishchenko/tmatrix/>

3) The mopsmap package for pre-calculated scattering properties of rotationally symmetric particles, publicly available here: <https://mopsmap.net/> and graphical user interface: <https://mopsmap.net/v1.0/mopsmap.php>

4) The TAMUdust2020 database for pre-calculated scattering properties of irregular hexahedral particles, publicly available here: <https://zenodo.org/records/4711247>

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- Decision makers

Project partners

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

No

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

No

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

No

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

Data identifiers

DOI

Scattering imulations output will be provided through Zenodo linked to DOI

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

DataCite Metadata Schema

Metadata will be provided through Zenodo

3.1.1.3 What type(s) of metadata?

Descriptive

We offer descriptive metadata that enriches data or information resources with detailed information about their content, context, and structure, thereby improving their findability and practical use.

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

No

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

Yes

3.1.1.7 How are searchable metadata provided?

- Registry/Catalogue
- Metadata repository

The NOA's metadata for the scattering datasets can be found in OPENAIRE (<https://explore.openaire.eu>) and EOSC-portal ([EOSC-portal.eu](https://eosc-portal.eu))

3.1.1.8 Are keywords provided in the metadata?

Yes

aerosol , scattering, optical properties , microphysical properties, dust, smoke, pollution, marine

3.1.1.9 Are metadata harvestable?

Yes

Metadata can be harvested for data sharing through the Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting (OAI-PMH).

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

Zenodo

3.2.1.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?

Yes

- Follows repository standards
- Details terms of use
- Has an open access content policy
- Supports retention
- Follows metadata standards
- Supports mid- and long-term preservation
- Has data security mechanisms in place

3.2.1.5 Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?

Yes

3.2.1.6 Does the repository(ies) resolve the identifiers to a digital object?

Zenodo automatically register a DOI for a record once it is published

3.2.1.7 Does the repository support versioning?

Yes

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

Single scattering properties of polydisperse randomly oriented aerosol particles of different types

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open

Open, although a certain embargo period might be applied

3.2.2.5 Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset / output?

No

3.2.2.8 Is the described dataset / output supported by a data access committee?

No

3.2.2.9 Please specify how the dataset / output will be accessed during and after the project ends

Throughout the project's duration, the dataset might be subject to an embargo of up to two years. During this period, access to the data will be restricted, but project partners can obtain access using specific tokens. Once the embargo period concludes and the project is completed, the dataset will become publicly available, and accessible to all under the CC BY 4.0 license.

After the data become publicly accessible, it will not be possible to identify individuals who access the data. However, during the embargo period, access is controlled through tokens that are nominally issued to specific, selected partners.

3.2.2.10 Please specify how long after the project has ended the dataset / output will be made accessible for

Items will be retained for the lifetime of the repository in Zenodo. This is currently the lifetime of the host laboratory CERN, which currently has an experimental programme defined for the next 20 years at least.

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

Yes

Yes. However, we will not have closed datasets

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.3 Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?

Yes

Direct links are provided

3.2.3.4 Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?

Yes

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

3.3.3 Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?

Yes

DataCite Metadata Schema

3.3.7 Does the described dataset / output provide qualified references with other outputs?

Yes

The dataset will be linked with the related scientific articles and to the aerosol optical properties used for developing operators for data assimilation in atmospheric models (CERTAINTY WP2, Task 2.2)

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

The embargo period is 2 years from the moment of publication.

3.4.2 What reusability and / or reproducibility methods are followed?

- Readme files
- Data cleaning
- Analyses
- Units of measurement
- Negative results sharing

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

Yes

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

Yes

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

Yes

Input data provenance will be linked in the metadata.

3.4.6 What documented procedures for quality assurance do you have in place?

- Data conform to format specification
- Consistency verified with data models and standards

We will compare the simulated data with aerosol models from the literature and laboratory measurements.

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

0

Euro

- Storage
- Archiving
- Re-use
- Security

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Other

Data will be provided through Zenodo

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

Anna Gialitaki (orcid:0000-0001-9270-8361)

5.1 Data Security

5.1.1 What security measures are followed?

Passwords

5.1.2 What conditions do the security measures meet?

- Data access
- Data storage
- Data transmission
- Data recovery
- Data sharing

5.1.3 How will you preserve the described dataset / output in the long term?

Items will be retained for the lifetime of the repository in Zenodo. This is currently the lifetime of the host laboratory CERN, which currently has an experimental programme defined for the next 20 years at least.

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

no

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

No

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

Yes

7.1.2 Documentation of other procedures

All the minimum conditions listed in Science Europe Guidance Document are covered by the WP6 Open Science and Data management

ASKOS campaign dataset

Ground based remote sensing data used to investigate the aerosol effect on cloud and precipitation formation in warm and mixed phase clouds

1. Aerosol profiles from multi-wavelength polarization Raman lidar measurements
2. Aerosol optical depth (AOD) and columnar aerosol microphysical information (volume size distribution, refractive index, single scattering albedo, absorption and extinction AOD, asymmetry factor) from multi-wavelength sun-photometer measurements
3. Horizontal wind speed and direction, attenuated backscatter coefficient (1.5 μm), and vertical velocity from scanning Doppler wind lidar measurements
4. Liquid water path (LWP), and integrated water vapor content (IWV) from microwave radiometer measurements
5. Doppler velocity, cloud reflectivity, liquid water content (LWC) profiles from cloud radar measurements
6. Total (Global), direct and diffuse shortwave irradiances (280-2800 nm), the net shortwave (300-2800 nm) and longwave (4500-42000 nm) radiation, and the upwelling and downwelling irradiance during daytime from actinometric station measurements

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

Re-used

Ground based remote sensing data collected during the ASKOS campaign in Cabo Verde (<https://askos.space.noa.gr/>) will be used to study the aerosol effect on cloud and precipitation formation in warm and mixed phase clouds

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Observational

1.1.5 What is its format?

netcdf

ASCII

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

3000000000000

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To obtain information
- To share information
- To improve a product
- To combine with other data

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

ASKOS Campaign Dataset publicly available in ESA validation data centre:

<https://evdc.esa.int/publications/askos-campaign-dataset/>

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities

Project partners

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

Yes

An Overview of the ASKOS Campaign in Cabo Verde

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

Yes

The ASKOS data are currently available upon request and will be publicly available by September 2023 through the EVDC portal (ESA Validation Data Center; evdc.esa.int)

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

No

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

Data identifiers

DOI

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

No

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

ESA Validation Data Center (EVDC)

<https://evdc.esa.int/publications/askos-campaign-dataset/>

ESA Validation Data Center is a central, long-term repository in Europe for archiving and exchange of correlative data for validation of atmospheric composition products from satellite platforms.

EVDC builds on the previous ENVISAT Cal/Val database system in operation at NILU since the early 2000s, and provides tools for extraction, conversion and archival of a large amount of EO data. The objective of the EVDC is to provide an online information system that supports users in managing and exploiting campaign datasets for Earth Observation missions and applications.

The database helps as a tool to monitor the quality and availability of the data provided by the data acquisition teams contracted by ESA, and it aims to support field campaigns over various seasons and latitudes.

To facilitate exchange of validation data among investigators and missions a common effort between the GEOMS group that consists of representatives of NASA, ESA, the NDACC and related universities and organizations, has led to a set of harmonized guidelines, The Generic Earth Observation Metadata Standard (GEOMS) guidelines. EVDC is fully compatible with GEOMS.

Through collaboration with the ECMWF, EVDC is providing access to daily updated analyses and forecast data files of global gridded meteorological parameters.

3.2.1.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?

Yes

- Follows repository standards
- Details terms of use
- Has an open access content policy
- Supports retention
- Provides Open Access content (free at the point of use)
- Assigns PIDs

- Supports mid- and long-term preservation
- Supports authentication and authorization of users
- Has data security mechanisms in place

3.2.1.5 Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?

Yes

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

ASKOS Campaign Dataset

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open

Dataset is openly available through the ESA Validation Data Centre

3.2.2.5 Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset / output?

No

3.2.2.8 Is the described dataset / output supported by a data access committee?

No

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

No

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

0

Euro

- Storage
- Archiving
- Re-use

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Other

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

no

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

No

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

ACTRIS ground-based remote sensing data to quantify aerosol-cloud interaction processes

ACTRIS ground based remote sensing data used to investigate the aerosol effect on cloud and precipitation formation in warm and mixed phase clouds:

1. Aerosol profiles from multi-wavelength polarization Raman lidar measurements
2. Aerosol optical depth (AOD) and columnar aerosol microphysical information (volume size distribution, refractive index, single scattering albedo, absorption and extinction AOD, asymmetry factor) from multi-wavelength sun-photometer measurements

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

Re-used

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Observational

1.1.5 What is its format?

netcdf

ascii

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

30000000000

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To obtain information
- To share information
- To improve a product
- To combine with other data

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities

Project partners

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

Data identifiers

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

No

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

No

3.4.6 What documented procedures for quality assurance do you have in place?

Details of ACTRIS quality control and assurance can be found here:

<https://www.actris.eu/catalogue-of-services/services>

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

0

Euro

- Storage
- Archiving
- Re-use
- Security

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Other

Project

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

No

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

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